

**FATHER – SON RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SANTIAGO
AND MANOLIN IN THE OLD MAN AND THE SEA****Zinatdinov Ajiniyaz Kuralbay uli**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20790318>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 16th June 2026Accepted: 18th June 2026Online: 20th June 2026**KEYWORDS***Love; father-son relationship; Ernest Hemingway; The old man and the sea;***ABSTRACT**

The purpose of this study is to thoroughly analyze, identify and demonstrate the love of little boy, Manolin, towards old man as if he was Manolin's real father or Santiago's love towards Manolin as if he was Santiago's genetic son from The Old man and the sea by Ernest Hemingway. The source of this study is Hemingway's The old man and the sea. Firstly, the source text has been read thoroughly and the lines containing the message of either Santiago's or Manolin's love have been identified. Then, findings were sorted out according to their belongings to the old man or boy, which were divided into several subdivisions in terms of the meaning of the message that is given by the author through words: Manolin's moral support and Manolin's materialistic support, and, Santiago's concern about Manolin's benefit, Santiago's proudness (thanking) of Manolin and Santiago's missing Manolin.

The old man and the sea is one of the most popular literary works and masterpieces of the 20th century and of Ernest Hemingway. The novel contains a wide range of symbols, themes, and values concerning various aspects of life; thus, it has been appealing to both young and old readers, amateur and professional researchers.

To date, Setyaningsih (2015) analyzed the novel's symbolic aspects and Li, Hongxia and Xiaobing Qi (2016) conduct research on the role of little boy, Manolin, and his significance in the novel to showcase the endurance, grace and heroism of the old man, Santiago, via Manolin's loyalty and belief in Santiago. Besides the aforementioned scholars, the novel was investigated by Xie (2008), Nezam & Pirnajmuddin (2012), Muhammed (2011), and Chakraborty (2013) from various perspectives.

This research was carried out as a supplement to the work Li, Hongxia, and Xiaobing Qi (2016) and other studies conducted. In Li, Hongxia, and Xiaobing Qi's (2016) study, the theme of love of Manolin towards Santiago is highlighted; however, the quantity of examples is not sufficient. Therefore, the principal goal of this study is, first, to show the father-son love between two chief characters and provide with more examples from source text and, by this way, to supplement the part "The Symbol of Love in Manolin" of Li, Hongxia, and Xiaobing Qi's (2016).

Our research begins with the lines, expressing moral and materialistic care of the boy, Manolin, towards Santiago as if towards his own father. Lines which convey in itself the

meaning of moral aid, especially by Manolin, have been found in a great number throughout the novel. Even some of them, either word by word repeated or possessing the same meaning, have been omitted during the process of sorting the material out. In terms of lines regarding materialistic care, one can identify such kind of lines also in a sufficient number. First, findings about Manolin's moral care will be discussed and then materialistic will be followed.

From the very beginning the story commences with the following lines: "...In the first forty days a boy had been with him." (p. 1), which is already the message about Manolin's loyalty towards the old man. Then, Manolin was forced by parents to go fishing with other boats. Even in that situation the boy is still eager to show his assistance to Santiago no matter in what way. Thus, first he offers to go with the old man, in spite of refusal of his parents, which was kindly refused by the old man, since he is well-aware of the decision of Manolin's parents and granting the boy the best choice he considered as true. Then, Manolin shares the idea of sailing closer to the boat on which he fishes; however, even this attempt was in vain, for the old man knows the discrepancy of the character and fishing style of his colleagues.

Even after several futile efforts, Manolin does not give up. He keeps on endeavoring to support Santiago physically. Witnessing the anxiety of old man after another day with no fish, the boy endeavors to assist by carrying his fishing tools both before and after the fishing. Also, so as to set old man's soul from anxiety of 'could not catch a fish for the last eighty-four days', he repeatedly reminds his personal anti-record, which consists of 'eighty-seven days without fish...', followed by 'big ones every day for three weeks.' (p. 1). Besides, he asked Santiago to talk about the baseball and his favorite player, Di Maggio, about which and whom Santiago loves to talk. By this way, the boy let the old man forget about his unluckiness for some time. Moreover, complimenting style has also been applied via the following lines:

- "But are you strong enough now for a truly big fish?" (p.3).

- "There is no such fish if you are still strong as you say." (p.8).

- "I think they are equal." "And the best fisherman is you." "No. I know others better." "Que Va," the boy said. "There are many good fishermen and some great ones. But there is only you." "Thank you. You make me happy. I hope no fish will come along so great that he will prove us wrong." (p.p.7 - 8).

The last one, beyond any doubt, should be mentioned with more emphasis, for exactly those compliments possess a great role in keeping Santiago confident. After so many days with no fish, naturally confidence rate may begin to decrease; nevertheless, after hearing such compliments from Manolin and finding out that there is a person who still believes in his power, strength, skill, and ability, Santiago does not give up and keeps believing in his own strength to catch a truly big fish.

Last but not least, some cares done the day before the fishing day deserve truly special attention. Having returned from another 'no fish' day, Santiago cares about neither eating nor health, sleeping without blanket. But Manolin appears and persuades him to eat food and motivates by reminding that he will not be strong enough to catch a big fish if he does not eat anything. After supper, he also reminds him to sleep earlier to "be fresh in the morning." Then, "...The boy took the old army blanket off the bed and spread it over the back of the chair and over the old man's shoulders." (P. 5).

Manolin knows Santiago better than anyone else. He is well-aware of what Santiago loves to do and Manolin draws on these methods in order to cherish him. In other words, we can call Manolin as the controller or, let say, expert of changing of the old man's mood. All the examples above demonstrating love and care are normally observed between father and child in everyday life, that's why they were selected both by the author and researcher to demonstrate Manolin's affiliation about Santiago.

Alongside with moral support shown to the old man during the "grace" without fish, Manolin endeavors to support financially through purchasing him various things that Santiago is keen on having. At the beginning of the story, he proposed the old man beer and two fresh sardines. This offer is happily received by the old man. In addition, the night before the fishing day the boy brought Santiago supper and attempts to convince the old man to eat it once more.

Last but not least, towards the end of the novel, after returning with the skeleton of marlin, "He (the boy) went into the Terrace and asked for a can of coffee. "Hot and with plenty of milk and sugar in it." "Anything more?" "No. Afterwards I will see what he can eat." (p. 46). "The boy carried the hot can of coffee up to the old man's shack and sat by him until he woke. Once it looked as though he were waking. But he had gone back into heavy sleep and the boy had gone across the road to borrow some wood to heat the coffee. Finally, the old man woke. "Don't sit up," the boy said. "Drink this." (P. 46).

From the examples presented above once more proves the fact that Manolin knows what he is doing. He has been with the old man since he was five and exactly knows, even better than his own daughter, which might appear quite sarcastic assimilation, what kind of coffee the old man prefers or which beer he loves to drink. To be more specific, Manolin loves to care about the old man just as like son loves his father. For sure, such cares has not been done to his genetic father, which showcases the unbelievable closeness between these two characters. Manolin strongly believes and supports Santiago, even if Santiago's own daughter does not, and for Manolin there is no fisherman better than Santiago. In a few words, Manolin is practically ready for everything for the sake of Santiago, no matter will it be moral support or materialistic one.

Santiago's love towards the boy

As Manolin loves Santiago like his real father, the old man also is not apathetic about Manolin in terms of father – son relationship. Sufficient examples, despite being reasonably less as compared to the lines expressing the love of Manolin to the old man, could be mentioned so as to prove Santiago's love to the boy. The sorted-out findings belonging to the old man, in its turn, have been divided into three various categories: first, old man's concerning about the boy's benefit; second, Santiago's thanking to Manolin and, last, Santiago's missing the boy.

Old man's worry about boy's benefit

This subdivision is called old man's concerning about boy's benefit. It is not real concerning and it does not indicate that the boy is in danger. The case is that we have already mentioned about Manolin's wish to go fishing alongside with the old man, which was immediately refused by Santiago. It is no secret that Santiago himself desires to go fishing with Manolin. However, he refused, or, more precisely, has to refuse the given offer. One key reason can be stated for this act: firstly, Santiago does not want to frustrate boy's parents and

so as not to leave the boy in an uncomfortable situation in front of his parents. Additionally, by responding “You’re with a lucky boat. Stay with them.” (p.1) Santiago knows that it will be better for Manolin with others rather than with him, because there is fear about not catching fish again, which will bring both the old man and the boy no benefit; therefore, Santiago selects just to let the boy stay with other, however luckier than him, fishermen.

Then on the day of ‘hunting’ Santiago wakes Manolin up early in the morning, which tortures the boy enough. As we all know that it is quite challenging for the young generation to wake up so early and Santiago comprehends this, too. Having felt this, Santiago felt sorry and apologized, which is the frequently happening situation principally between parents and their son. In other words, the pain of Manolin tortures his “fishing father’ as well.

Santiago’s gratitude to Manolin

One can notice several times Santiago’s proudness (thanking) of the boy’s acts or, let’s say, kindness. Initially, it begins when Manolin buys a bottle of beer to Santiago, for which he gratitude with the words “You bought me a beer,” the old man said. “You are already a man.” (p. 2). Then Santiago’s love was clearly and directly expressed when he “looked at him with his sun-burned, confident loving eyes.” (p.3). The last one is when they are having dinner together, old man replied ‘That’s very kind of you’ (p. 3) for purchasing for the old man another bottle of beer. As the care done by his/her son makes any parents proud and happy, Boy’s care makes Santiago happy, for through Manolin he feels what it is like the care of son towards his father.

Santiago’s missing the boy

Parents’ missing his child is a natural condition. Man’s missing the person who is not relative blood is extraordinary matter. During fishing, Santiago acknowledged his missing for the boy several times, even he repeated it about several times during fishing alone in the sea. His missing is as a consequence of harsh condition, yet is true. First, he began missing when he was surprised about the habit of talking to himself. He realized that this habit began after boy’s leaving him and fishing on another boat, which can be referred as the first message of Santiago missing. Also, at that time he also remembered what they did together while fishing. Second, while struggling with the giant marlin and when the old man is in need for supplementary assistance of someone, he repeated the line ‘I wish I had the boy’ (p.p. 16 – 20) about seven times both aloud and silently. Last, at the very end of the novel, Santiago even himself confessed to his missing the boy. Those lines are as following:

- “The ocean is very big and a skiff is small and hard to see,” the old man said. He noticed how pleasant it was to have someone to talk to instead of speaking only to himself and to the sea. “I missed you,” he said. (p. 47)

In conclusion, even if the old man, Santiago, and the boy, Manolin, are not relatives in blood, they were described by the author just as like they are father and son. People of the village laugh at the old man, name him as an unlucky old fisherman, repeating that his ‘spring is already far behind. Nevertheless, those comments do not affect to the old man’s confidence even slightly, for there is someone who believes in him, supports him and, most importantly, loves him like his own father, Manolin. In its turn, Santiago also endeavors to wish merely good things to the boy as parents wished to their child, misses him and is proud of him for his

being such a good person. All the examples demonstrated in this research supports the fact that Santiago loves Manolin like his own son and vice-versa.

Cited works:

- Chakraberty, P. (2013). A celebration of humanity: The ethical and the ethereal aspects of Hemingway's *The Old Man and the Sea*. *International Journal of English and Literature*, 4(9), 440-443.
- Hemingway, Ernest. 1994. *The Old Man and the Sea*. London, England: Arrow Books.
- Li, Hongxia, and Xiaobing Qi. "On Manolin's Symbolic Meaning in the *Old Man and the Sea*." *International Conference on Humanities and Social Science 2016*. Atlantis Press, 2016.
- Muhammed, M. M. (2011). Individuality in Ernest Hemingway's "The old man and the sea". *Journal of Kerbala University*, 9(01), 1-7.
- Nezam, A., & Pirnajmuddin, H. (2012). Translation of Ellipsis as a Stylistic Feature: Hemingway's *The Old Man and the Sea* and Its Persian Translations. *Journal of Language Teaching & Research*, 3(6).
- Setyaningsih, H.S. (2015). Optimistic Life Reflected In the Style of Ernest Hemingway's *The Old Man and the Sea*.
- Xie, Y. (2008). Hemingway's Language Style and Writing Techniques in "The Old Man and the Sea". *English language teaching*, 1(2), 156-158.